

The contribution of social sciences driven user studies to the development of human-centered artificial intelligence

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Abstract. The aim of the paper is to indicate the categories of results that can be obtained in the course of social sciences inspired user studies and to discuss their potential for further development of human-centered XAI. The paper reviews selected qualitative methods and techniques, including: in-depth interviews, focus groups, Delphi method, usability tests with the TAP protocol, UX techniques and observations with the guided tour module as examples of research focused on diagnosing users' opinions, behaviors or experiences. A case study of the implementation of selected methods and techniques in an interdisciplinary research project in the field of XAI was discussed, showing in practice the value of methods driven from social science in the context of AI research. As a result, preliminary conclusions were formulated regarding a new approach to the evaluation of XAI methods, as well as prospects for further research.

Keywords: Explainable Artificial Intelligence, Human-centered Artificial Intelligence, User Studies, Social Science Methods.

1 Background and motivation

The need to include users in the process of evaluating explainable artificial intelligence (XAI) methods is increasingly emphasized in the subject literature, especially in relation to critical areas such as medicine, economics and security. As Arrieta et al. stated, XAI: “(...) 1) produce more explainable models while maintaining a high level of learning performance (e.g., prediction accuracy), and 2) enable humans to understand, appropriately trust, and effectively manage the emerging generation of artificially intelligent partners” (2020, p. 83).

It has clearly been stated numerous times in highly cited papers in the field of computer science that users should not only be recipients of final AI products, but also an active participants in the process of designing, testing and evaluating AI solutions (Miller, 2019) (Ghassemi, Oakden-Rayner & Beam, 2021) (Longo et al. 2023). This is important not only in terms of providing people with user-friendly, understandable and positive experiences with AI products, but also in terms of building public trust in AI by increasing the degree of its transparency and understandability.

Developing research on artificial intelligence created for and with the cooperation of humans requires a multilateral, interdisciplinary approach, which is noted by authors in the field of computer science. As L. Longo et al. emphasizes: "XAI has evolved into an exceedingly multidisciplinary, interdisciplinary, and transdisciplinary field" (2023, p. 2). In this context, the contribution of social sciences is pointed out as particularly valuable, as it is a domain that have a long, well-established tradition and methodology

of conducting user studies. As T. Miller rightly stated, a large part of current studies on XAI is based on: "researchers' intuitions of what constitutes a 'good' explanation" (2019, p. 2), which may be misleading due to the fact that: "very experts who understand decision-making models the best are not in the right position to judge the usefulness of explanations to lay users" (Miller, 2019, p. 2). It is therefore necessary to conduct extensive research with users taking inspiration from well-established and proven social science methods.

Drawing direct inspiration from the postulates presented in papers by Ghassemi, Oakden-Rayner & Beam, L. Longo et al, T. Miller and other authors, who clearly stated the need to involve users in the evaluation of AI explanations, and thus the need to examine their needs and feelings and behaviors; the author of this paper systematically characterized the key methods and techniques of qualitative user research, proving their usefulness for computer science on specific examples and by discussing a case study.

2. Objective and contribution

The aim of the paper is to indicate the categories of results that can be obtained in the course of social sciences inspired user studies and to discuss their potential for further development of human-centered artificial intelligence research. The specific objectives of the study include:

- identifying key methods and techniques of user studies in social sciences,
- developing a typology of user studies methods and techniques depending on the category of obtained results,
- synthetic characterization of identified methods and techniques in relation to their potential usefulness for the evaluation of XAI methods,
- presenting an example of practical use of the potential of social sciences for AI research,
- formulating perspectives for further research integrating the potential of social sciences and engineering.

The paper reviews selected methods and techniques for examining users' opinions, behaviors and experiences, including: in-depth interviews, focus groups, Delphi method, usability tests with the TAP protocol, participant observations with the guided tour module, as well as UX questionnaires and Kano approach. The attention was focused exclusively on qualitative methods and techniques as an approach typical for social sciences.

A case study of the implementation of selected methods and techniques in an interdisciplinary research project in the field of XAI was discussed, showing in practice the value of methods driven from social science in the context of AI research.

As a result, preliminary conclusions were formulated regarding a new approach to the evaluation of XAI methods and prospects for further research were outlined.

3. Methods

To establish the state of research and select key methods and techniques of user studies the method of literature review was used. With regard to the subject literature, a systematic search was carried out according to the adopted queries in database indexing journals with high IF - Scopus, and additionally, selected resources indexed by Google Scholar were also included. Methodological papers on user studies in the field of social science published in English in the years 2014-2024 were taken into account. The collected material was initially analyzed qualitatively based on abstracts and keywords to identify the most relevant contributions. A selected corpus of publications covering methodological works in the social sciences, consisting mainly of papers or monographs, was then further reviewed to identify the most frequently repeated references to user research methods and techniques. It is worth noting that at this stage many publications that related to social science research methodology, but did not necessarily directly concern user studies, were rejected. Publications concerning only quantitative methods were also deliberately omitted, with a conscious decision to focus only on qualitative methods as more useful from the point of view of the subject of considerations in the article.

Then, a case study of the implementation of selected methods and techniques in practice in an interdisciplinary project in the field of XAI was described. The purpose of the study, the used methods and the categories of results obtained were characterized, drawing conclusions regarding the usefulness of user research methods taken from social sciences for developing a new approach to the evaluation of XAI methods.

4. Relevant subject literature

In the social sciences, methodological works are published relatively frequently, both in the form of short papers dealing with narrow issues, e.g. relating to a specific method or technique or a specific area of their application, as well as in the form of monographs and collective publications dealing with methods and techniques of research in social sciences in a broad, review manner (Eriksson & Kovalainen, 2015) (McNabb, 2016). Many papers drew attention to the classic methodological dilemma related to using a quantitative vs. qualitative approach, as well as the pros and cons of both (Gerring, 2017) (Baškarada, S. & Koronios, 2018), often emphasizing the benefits of using the mix-method approach (Tashakkori & Teddlie, 2021). In relation to qualitative research, special attention was paid to the need to maintain strict methodological rigor, the need to thoroughly document the research process, and importance was attached to the personal and social skills of researchers (Johnson & Rasulovala, 2017) (Johnson, Adkins & Chauvin, 2020). Many works also referred to difficulties related to the development of qualitative material and emphasized ethical and legal issues related to conducting research involving people (Jerolmack & Murphy, 2019) (Shaw, 2023).

5. Results

As a result of the literature review several of the most popular user studies methods and techniques taken from the field of social science research were selected and synthetically characterized, emphasizing the categories of results they can provide. Finally, a practical example of implementing some methods in an interdisciplinary project in the field of XAI was described.

5.1 Methods and techniques of user studies aimed at obtaining opinions

One of the basic qualitative methods for obtaining information from users is an in-depth interview based on sourcing information during a conversation. It may take a structured form, in which the researcher strictly follows a predefined pattern of questions; unstructured form that gives the researcher greater flexibility in reacting to the situation and conducting the conversation in various directions within a defined area of interest; or semi-structured, mixed approach. The structured variant allows for greater comparability of research conducted by different scientists and is also easier to develop. On the other hand, it may limit the framework of the study and favor the omission of observations spontaneously reported by users and not assumed in the original concept of the study (Brinkmann, 2014). The selection of the interview variant, as well as the number and way of formulating questions, the duration of the interview and the circumstances of its conduct (in the research laboratory vs. in the natural environment of the respondents) depend on the objectives of the study. The advantages of the interview, regardless of the variant adopted, include its universal nature and the high flexibility, which allows it to be used as the main method of obtaining information from users or as an auxiliary tool. The scope of interview results depends not only on the adopted parameters, but also on the researcher's communication and psychological competences, as well as on the selection of respondents and their individual characteristics (Knott et al., 2022).

A variant of interviews are focus groups, often used in public opinion research and marketing studies. Focus, is a form of discussion on a specific, usually quite narrow topic, led by a moderator in a group of deliberately selected people (Nuttavuthisit, 2019). The advantage of focus groups over one-on-one interviews is the ability to observe how respondents' opinions, beliefs and preferences change in social situations under the influence of group dynamics. This allows for a more realistic representation of human decision-making processes, taking into account their social nature. On the other hand, focus groups may not be the most effective method in researching sensitive topics (Kruger et al., 2019).

An interesting method of collecting group opinions is Delphi method. It involves asking questions to a group of deliberately selected experts, often representing various fields of research and areas of practical activities, in order to collect, average and develop a consensus of their opinions on complex, multidimensional phenomena. Answers to questions are collected through individual contact between the researcher and particular experts. Then, the researcher prepares conclusions and sends them to all involved experts, asking them to comment on the results until opinions on a given topic are shared and averaged (Lund, 2020). This method is particularly useful in developing

scenarios for the future, as well as in analyzing complex problems and controversial issues on which it is difficult to reach a consensus using other methods. The disadvantage is the time-consuming nature of this process, difficulty in obtaining the involvement of high-quality experts and the loss of the individual character of qualitative research in favor of averaging and reaching consensus. However, it is still a valuable method of obtaining expert opinions in relation to complex problems.

5.2 Methods and techniques of user studies aimed at diagnosing behavior

Usability tests are one of the most popular methods of testing the usability of websites and applications, providing real insight into the actual way people interact with various information systems. This aspect distinguishes usability tests from methods and techniques aimed at obtaining opinions (declarations), such as previously discussed interviews or focus groups. It is important to note that the role of usability tests is to validate systems, not people, however, it is still possible to gain insight into their behavior in relation to the system. During tests conducted by a moderator according to a research scenario, users watch the tested websites or applications (sometimes also prototypes) and perform practical tasks typical for using a specific type of system. Users' voices and images are recorded, and sometimes the time required to complete tasks is also measured. The entire process is observed by an additional person or group of people invisible to the test participant through using a one-way mirror or sharing the desktop (Geisen & Bergstrom, 2017). Think-aloud protocol (TAP), which involves encouraging the test participant to constantly verbalize the actions taken, emotions felt or difficulties experienced, is a popular module added to usability tests which allows to understand better users' motivations to engage in specific behaviors and provides insight into their thought processes (Wolcott & Lobczowski, 2021).

Another classic way of researching users' actions and behaviors is observation, which can be either participatory - when researchers are simultaneously participants of the situation under study, or non-participatory, when they remain fully neutral and separate from the research context. Observation is based on the process of knowing the characteristics of people, objects or environments in a purposeful way using researchers senses (Ciesielska, Boström & Öhlander, 2017). Observation, regardless of the variant, involves the perception, collection, description and interpretation of data obtaining from the environment, without changing it, which is important and distinguishes this method from experiment. The advantages of observation as a research method include, first of all, the ability to directly, undisturbedly learn about human behavior as it occurs in natural conditions. The disadvantages include the possibility of distortion of the research due to the imperfection of human senses, the subjective nature of the research due to the personal characteristics of the observer and sometimes also the dynamics of interaction between the researcher and the participant.

A research technique aimed at diagnosing human behavior, that is currently gaining popularity in social sciences, is so-called guided tour. It is a way of learning about human activities in which the subject (participant) of research acts as a guide in his or her space (physical or virtual) and presents, tells and shows it from his or her subjective perspective (Thomson, 2018). This is particularly useful in examining behaviors and

routines practiced by people intuitively and often difficult to detect in other types of research due to their obvious nature to the research participant but interesting and unknown from the researcher's point of view. The disadvantage of using this technique is that control over the course of the study is largely given to the participants and it is difficult to predict the categories of study results. Also noteworthy is the high degree of subjectivity of the data obtained, which, depending on the context, may be considered as an advantage or a disadvantage.

5.3 Methods and techniques of user studies aimed at examination of experiences

Nowadays, one of the most important categories of user studies is research focused on understanding user experiences. It is assumed that it is no longer enough to design a system that will be functional, but it is necessary to design it in such a way that using the system is a positive, unique and memorable experience for the user. It fits into the broader context of the assumptions of the so-called experience economy, defined as an economic model in which the highest value for customers, for which they are willing to pay, is not the product or service itself, but the experience related to the commercial process (Wójcik, 2019). Researching experiences is not an easy task due to their highly subjective nature, but many methods and techniques in this area have already been developed.

One of the most popular and longest-standing technique is the user experience questionnaire. It is a technique that uses a research tool based on a questionnaire divided into sections related to specific features of the tested system in relation to users' feelings. The individual sections contain terms reflecting the user's emotions on a scale from terms related to negative experiences to positive ones (Wöbbekind, Mandl & Womser-Hacker, 2021). The advantages of this technique include the simplicity of its use and the ease of processing the results by the researcher. The disadvantage is the rather general nature of the results obtained, giving an overall idea of the user's feelings, but leaving no room for explanations or specification of their source. In this context, the Kano approach may be helpful as a complementary technique. In this type of study, users are asked to indicate the features of the tested system that are considered by them as attractive, expected, indifferent, necessary or are considered a failure. This is a technique often used in researching people for marketing purposes because it allows to translate users' subjective feelings into specialized language and organize people's often chaotic reflections about products and services into clear categories of results (Park, Lee & Back, 2020). The disadvantages of this technique include the relatively high difficulty for users in completing Kano questionnaires, especially on their own without the assistance of a researcher. The study requires a thorough explanation to participants of how to define the individual features of the system under study about which they are asked. However, if used correctly, it can provide valuable insight into the features of the system, taking into account users' experiences related to them, and also allow for comparison of the tested system with other, similar ones.

5.4. Implementations of user studies in the field of artificial intelligence research – literature review

In the subject literature, descriptions of different practical application of user studies in the field of artificial intelligence research can be found, although not that often. Different meta-analyses of the literature on XAI available so far, show that there are several dozen relevant papers that refer, at least to some extent, to user studies, however in the individual papers it is often difficult to find detailed descriptions of the applied user research methodology with a clear indication categories of results obtained. For instance, a literature review by Rong et al. done on a group of 97 papers on human-based XAI evaluations, clearly showed that: "user evaluations are still rather sparse and incorporate hardly any insights from cognitive or social sciences" (2024). Similarly, a literature review conducted on a group of 58 papers by Haque, Islam and Mikalef showed that: "limited number of studies exist that measure the user perceptions of the transparency, understandability, and usability of an XAI system" (2023).

In a relatively few papers reporting specific examples of XAI user research, the most common were those referring to diagnosing users' opinions; rarely papers show the practical use of social sciences' methods and techniques to study behaviors and experiences.

Interesting example of using interview to diagnose opinions is reported by Liao, Gruen and Miller. Authors interviewed 20 UX designers working on various AI products to identify gaps between the current approach to XAI and contemporary design practices focused on building user experiences. It is worth noting, however, that this study did not take into account the opinions of end users (Liao, Gruen & Miller, 2020). The literature review showed that focus groups were a particularly popular method of researching opinions of AI users, especially in sensitive areas such as safety, medicine or finance. Example can be paper by Aitken et al. in which the results were reported from a series of focus research conducted with various target groups in the banking sector. The results of the study allowed to determine users' the needs, preferences, but also concerns related to AI (Aitken et al. 2020). Rarely, the Delphi method was also used to diagnose opinions on AI. An example can be the study by Boesl, Prassler and Bode, which indicates the potential of the Delphi method as a non-biased alternative for other types of predictive research on technology development (2017).

Overall it can be concluded that rather unsatisfactory number of examples of the implementation of user studies in the practice of AI research, especially in the layer of diagnosing behaviors and experiences - despite numerous calls for such activities in the subject literature - shows a certain gap between theory and practice and reveals scope for further research. To fill this gap and show the practical application of selected social science methods and techniques in the field of XAI research, a case study related an interdisciplinary research project was described.

5.5 Practical implementation of selected types of user studies in the area of XAI - case study

The aim of the research described as a case study was to examine the extent to which explanations generated by artificial intelligence are understandable to various groups

of users, especially to people without a background in computer science and engineering.

A tabular dataset on the edibility of wild mushrooms was selected for the study. A group of domain experts - mycologists and a group of students representing various levels of knowledge about fungi (usually low to medium) and various degrees of experience in data analytics and visualization (students of humanities and social sciences, as well as students of computer science) were invited to participate in the study.

A mix-method research approach was used based on a combination of various qualitative elements. An experiment based on an adapted usability tests scheme combined with the TAP protocol was conducted with all participants to observe in practice the way they interacted with AI explanations and the actual level of their understanding of XAI (behavior research level). Additionally, to determine users' feelings and experiences related to the use of XAI, simplified UX questionnaires and elements of the Kano approach were used (experience research level). Finally, unstructured interviews were woven into the main core of the experiment which was particularly useful during the study with a group of domain experts who, due to their knowledge, had many comments to share, especially about the quality of the dataset and the consequences of using AI explanations in practice (opinion research level).

Overall 39 research individual sessions with users were conducted which is considered to be a high number of participants in qualitative research. Each session lasted on average 2 hours which gave about 80 hours of recording converted into a text version so it could be analyzed further. Every hour of recording is about 20 pages of transcription which adds up to a sizable text corpus. Transcriptions provided by the software as a result of automatic processes were often not satisfactory in terms of quality for the purposes of the study so most transcriptions had to be either extensively edited or made manually from scratches. Finally, the transcriptions were subjected to the tagging process in accordance with the assumptions of content analysis procedure using MaxQDA software (Lindgren, Lundman & Graneheim, 2020).

The use of an original combination of various qualitative methods and techniques, oriented on obtaining different categories of results, provided unique insight into the problems of actual usefulness of AI explanations for users, opening up the possibility of a new way of evaluating XAI methods.

At the level of obtaining opinions, it was found that comments of non-expert students gave abundance of practical tips concerning improvements of the usability of AI explanations, especially in terms of aesthetics and information organization, while the comments of experts were almost solely focused on the quality of the dataset itself, especially in terms of its consistency with reality. Non-experts pointed out problems with the readability and comprehensibility of explanations, while clearly indicating their preferences for the types of explanations they consider to be more understandable and user-friendly. Domain experts, on the other hand, were focused on giving opinions, most often critical, about the quality of the dataset itself, highlighting the observed discrepancies between the model's performance and the biological reality of fungi.

At the level of diagnosing behaviors, it was found that AI explanations are treated by users as a tool enabling them to get cognitive access to the content generated by AI models. However, AI explanations clearly played different roles for different user

groups. For non-specialists XAI was treated as a potential source of knowledge that provide sole, yet usually insufficient access to AI model's output. For experts, on the other hand, viewing different types of XAI was considered to be an opportunity to compare their own knowledge with AI, which often ended with a critical assessment of the compliance of AI models with real life scenarios. With that note, conducted research allowed to conclude that, still for the group of domain experts XAI have a potential to serve proper mediation function as a gateway giving insight into the dataset itself and AI model's operation rules.

At the level of examining experiences, the methods and techniques used allowed to determine users overall emotions and feelings related to XAI, especially in terms of subjectively felt degree of difficulty, level of readability and aesthetics, and level of attention stimulation. It was also possible to determine the degree of difficulty of XAI methods compared to other types of data visualization previously seen by users in their everyday lives.

6. Conclusions

The described case study showed that user studies methods and techniques driven from social sciences can be successfully used in practice in interdisciplinary projects as a support for broadly understood computer science. It has been proven, that applying correctly selected combination of social science inspired methods and techniques to study the reception of AI explanations provided unique and otherwise difficult to obtain insight into their usefulness, understandability and user-friendliness. This input can be further used as a starting point for discussing new approaches to assessing the quality of AI explanation; one that takes into account the human-centered artificial intelligence perspective. This, in turn, at the application level, may lead to overall better adaptation of XAI to the needs of different groups of users.

It is worth noting, that user studies methods known from social sciences can be used - as in the case study described - to research users' opinions, behaviors and experiences connected with already existing solutions, or to diagnose users' needs, skills, preferences or fears before starting the design stage. The selection of an appropriate combination of methods and techniques from the wide methodological catalog of social sciences depends on the objectives of the study and the group of users being studied. However, it is worth triangulating different methods, taking into account the categories of results that are needed to be obtained.

Social sciences, with a long tradition of studying people, can offer methodological background useful for creating more user-friendly AI solutions. Providing people with clear, understandable and approachable explanations can serve not only to increase usability of XAI, but also raise the overall transparency of AI solutions, which is an important factor in the process of building social trust in AI. Including users in the loop of creating technical solutions addressed to them, at various stages, by examining their opinions, behaviors and experiences, is necessary to create proper human-centered AI.

7. Limitations and prospect for further research

It should be noted that due to the short format of the paper, only selected, qualitative methods and techniques were discussed, which of course does not constitute the full catalog of user studies methods known in social sciences. In this context, it would be worth considering in the future the usefulness of other, especially quantitative, methods and techniques of social sciences for the development of XAI, which were not the subject of considerations in this paper, however, they also carry considerable potential for the interdisciplinary cooperation.

The division into methods and techniques for examining opinions, behaviors and experiences adopted in this paper is conventional and serves to organize the discussion - due to the large diversity of variants of the described methods and techniques, there may be some elements falling into several different categories depending on the circumstances of the study. Nevertheless, thinking about the potential of methods and techniques taken from social sciences in terms of the categories of produced results, although burdened with certain limitations, can be used as a good, general direction for further considerations. In this context, it would be worth in the future to also develop other approaches to categorizing user studies results, than those presented in this study.

The paper constitutes a starting point towards a broader reflection on the methodological framework for developing a new approach to the evaluation of XAI methods. This challenging, multidimensional topic could undoubtedly benefit from closer cooperation between representatives of technical and social sciences. The foundations for the use of social science methods and techniques in AI research outlined in the paper will be continued and developed in subsequent publications.

Acknowledgments. The research discussed as a case study was conducted by the team: Magdalena Wójcik, Monika Krakowska, Magdalena Zych, Dorota Rak and Paloma Korycińska with the support of Szymon Bobek, Maciej Mozolewski and Grzegorz J. Nalepa as a part of XPM project funded by the National Science Centre, Poland under the CHIST-ERA programme grant agreement Np. 857925 (NCN UMO-2020/02/Y/ST6/00070). This paper is part of a project that has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme, under Grant Agreement number 101120406. The paper reflects only the authors' view and the EC is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Disclosure of Interests. Author was a paid participant in the XPM project funded by the National Science Centre, Poland under the CHIST-ERA programme grant agreement Np. 857925 (NCN UMO-2020/02/Y/ST6/00070). Author is a participant in the the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme, under Grant Agreement number 101120406.

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